

1 **Towards harmonization of metal analysis in plastics: comparison of acid digestion** 2 **protocols in conventional and compostable plastics**

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33

1 **Highlights**

- 2 • Six acid digestion protocols for plastics were validated on a reference material.
- 3 • Validated protocols were then applied to environmentally relevant end-use plastics.
- 4 • H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and H₂O₂ showed improved digestion performances.
- 5 • End-use plastics showed a more complex array of additives than the reference material.
- 6 • Future steps towards harmonized metal analysis protocols in plastics are suggested.

1 Towards harmonization of metal analysis in plastics: comparison of acid digestion 2 protocols in conventional and compostable plastics

3

4 Graphical abstract

5

6 Abstract

7 The analysis of metal-containing additives in plastic materials via acid digestion protocols has
8 attracted growing interest within the scientific community to understand the likely environmental
9 implications. However, the lack of protocol harmonization hinders data comparability within the
10 literature. Here, six microwave-assisted acid digestion protocols were employed for the analysis of
11 metals in plastics. These protocols utilized three different acid mixtures (HNO₃ combined with
12 H₂SO₄, HCl, or H₂O₂). After microwave-assisted digestion, an extra treatment using H₂O₂ at room
13 temperature was eventually performed to favour the complete mineralization of the samples.
14 Each protocol was firstly validated for seven metals (As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn) using a low-density
15 polyethylene (LDPE) certified reference material (ERM®-EC681m). Then, validated protocols were
16 applied on end-use materials including LDPE and compostable plastics (starch and poly(butylene-
17 adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT) blend).

18 The combination of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ with a further digestion step with H₂O₂ successfully passed the
19 validation for all metals (recoveries in the range 98.6 - 101.0%) and also yielded the highest
20 concentrations in end-use materials. This evidence establishes this procedure as the most effective
21 one. All other protocols resulted in a less efficient dissolution of the sample matrix, leading to lower
22 metal recoveries and to the formation of solid residues.

23 Furthermore, a notably higher variability was observed for metals in end-use plastics compared to
24 the reference material. This finding raises potential concerns regarding the types of additives
25 present in the polymers: the reference material contains a minimal amount of acid-soluble
26 additives, which may only limitedly represent the additive-rich plastics commonly found in the
27 environment.

28 This study proposes a first step towards the harmonization of acid digestion protocols and warns
29 about potential issues related to the accurate analysis of environmental end-use plastic materials,
30 due to their variable and complex chemical composition of additives.

31

32 **Highlights**

- 33 • Six acid digestion protocols for plastics were validated on a reference material.
- 34 • Validated protocols were then applied to environmentally relevant end-use plastics.
- 35 • H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ and H₂O₂ showed improved digestion performances.
- 36 • End-use plastics showed a more complex array of additives than the reference material.
- 37 • Future steps towards harmonized metal analysis protocols in plastics are suggested.

38

39 **Keywords**

40 Plastics; Polymers; Metals; Acid digestion; Additives; Microplastics;

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Plastic materials are used in an extensive range of application fields. Polymer producers designed
44 several inorganic, organic and organometallic compounds as additives to tune specifically required
45 properties of end-use plastic objects [1,2]. These intentionally added compounds and processing
46 aids include, for example, fillers, pigments, plasticizers, antioxidants, flame retardants, biocides, slip
47 agents and catalysts [1,3]. Other contaminants present in plastic products stem from residues or
48 impurities after manufacturing or recycling processes, and are collectively known as non-
49 intentionally added substances within the packaging field [4–6]. Several of these compounds may
50 pose adverse effects to biota including human, and their occurrence in plastics is consequently
51 receiving increasing attention from researchers, risk assessors and stakeholders: major concerns are
52 raised in the context of food contact materials and for plastics dispersed in environmental
53 compartments [7–13].

54 Although additives represent an essential part of plastics, their leaching from the consumer objects
55 is an important issue [14–19] several studies attempted to uncover the role of plastic materials as
56 potential sources or vectors of other organic and inorganic pollutants in the environment [20–23].
57 Here organic compounds have received major attention, whereas the analysis of inorganic
58 compounds, namely metals still remain scarcely explored: a minor number of studies focused on
59 the content of metals in plastic objects [14,18,24,25]. For example, some recent studies
60 preliminarily assessed the total mass fractions of metals in fragments [26–30] while a more limited
61 number of studies also tried to detect the bioavailable fractions and the speciation of metals
62 associated to environmental plastics [24,31–35]. The determination of the total metal content in
63 plastic is either way an essential process for both approaches [36,37].

64 Several methods and related techniques have been deployed to analyse metals in plastic polymers
65 [38–41]. Microwave-assisted acid digestion followed by the analysis of the obtained solution is the

66 most commonly applied procedure to determine the total content of metals in plastic, owing to the
67 higher sensibility and cost efficiency [36,37,42,43]. However, this approach covers a range of
68 methods in which the reagents and conditions used vary considerably. Additionally, only a few
69 polymeric certified reference materials (CRMs) which provide certified values of metal-containing
70 additives are available [37]. As a further complication, the end-use plastic materials have an
71 heterogenous composition of inorganic components, with different speciation of metals in the
72 polymer matrix (i.e. inorganic salts, oxides or organometallic compounds) which can complicate the
73 complete dissolution of the matrix, leading to the need of using several different procedures [44–
74 46]. All these constrains hinder an accurate measure of metals in plastics and limit data
75 comparability, too. A comprehensive agreement, i.e. harmonization, on the adequate acid mixtures
76 to be employed is still lacking and comparison of digestion performances among different protocols
77 are extremely rare [37].

78 In this context, this study aimed to tackle this issue by testing different microwave-assisted digestion
79 protocols using a standard CRM along with different end-use plastic objects. CRMs are in fact ideal
80 tools to verify the effectiveness of digestion procedures (Amaral et al., 2016). We firstly compared
81 the digestion mixtures for validation purposes using the CRM and the content of seven metals. Then,
82 we tested the analytical performances of these protocols on end-use conventional and compostable
83 plastics, considering their increasing use in the market [47–49]. This further comparison will allow
84 to explore the feasibility of a unique digestion method suitable for the study of the selected metals
85 in both conventional and compostable plastic materials.

86

87 **2. Materials and methods**

88 **2.1. Plastic materials selection and characterization**

89 Comparison of the digestion protocols was firstly performed with the CRM ERM[®]-EC681m
90 (polyethylene (elements, high level)). This was purchased from the Joint Research Centre of the
91 European Commission (JRC, Ispra, Italy) and comes as a green-coloured pellet made of low-density
92 polyethylene material (LDPE) spiked with metal-containing additives. Seven certified metals were
93 analysed in the present work: As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn, respectively. Their concentrations in
94 ERM[®]-EC681m cover a range from 17.0 ± 1.2 to 1170 ± 40 mg/kg ($U_{\text{certified}} k = 2$) [45]. Along with the
95 CRM, three end-use plastic samples (i.e., a commercially available LDPE and two compostable plastic
96 materials) were employed in the study. The end-use LDPE originated from white bags, obtained
97 from grocery stores. The compostable plastic materials also originated from grocery bags of green
98 and yellow colour, respectively (Fig. S1). These were made of a starch-based bioplastic blended with
99 biodegradable polyesters, pursuant to the EN 13432 standard [50,51]. In order to analyse a
100 homogenous sample, for the purpose of the study graphics and heat-sealed seams of the bags were
101 not digested.

102 A Fourier transformed infrared (FTIR) spectroscope (Thermo Scientific[™] (Waltham, MA, USA)
103 Nicolet[™] iS[™] 10) operating in attenuated total reflectance (ATR) mode was applied to confirm the
104 polymer composition. Thirty-two scans were collected for every sample in the 4000 cm^{-1} - 650 cm^{-1}
105 spectral interval, with a wavenumber resolution of 0.482 cm^{-1} . Prior to each measurement, a
106 background spectrum was recorded. The obtained spectra were smoothed using Savitzky–Golay
107 filter, then normalized on the maximum absorbance peak.

108

109 **2.2. Digestion protocols and metal analysis**

110 Six different digestion protocols were specifically tested (Table 1). These protocols include a
111 digestion step with heating assisted by a microwave system (protocols 1, 2 and 3) and a further
112 digestion step provided by H_2O_2 without any additional heating (protocols 1+H, 2+H and 3+H).

113 The choice of the digestion reagents was made upon the conditions commonly implemented in
114 literature. Hence, HNO₃ was considered as a prevalent oxidizing agent, in combination with other
115 auxiliary reagents, such as:

- 116 • H₂SO₄ (protocols 1 and 1+H), chosen for its potential to oxidize organic compounds [52–54];
- 117 • HCl (protocols 2 and 2+H), selected for its complexation and stabilization capacity towards some
118 metals [55,56];
- 119 • H₂O₂ (protocols 3 and 3+H), picked for its ability to enhance the role of HNO₃ and to contribute
120 in the digestion as an O₂ source [57].

121 Operatively, the dissolution of the plastic materials was obtained through microwave-assisted
122 digestions in a closed system (ETHOS One, Milestone MLS) equipped with 10
123 polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) vessels. For this, samples of each material were first cut using a
124 ceramic knife down to a size of ca. 5 mm and homogenously mixed. After, approximately 100 mg
125 was accurately weighted, and inserted into each pre-cleaned vessel, together with the required
126 mixture of acids. The materials were then digested applying a temperature ramp reaching 200 °C
127 for 45 minutes, consisting of a 30 minute heating and a 15 minute holding time [45].

128 Afterwards, a further digestion at room temperature was performed adding H₂O₂ after the initial
129 digestion for the protocols 1+H, 2+H and 3+H (Table 1). Hence, 0.1 ml of H₂O₂ was added to each
130 vessel and, following a gentle stirring, the reaction was allowed to continue for 30 minutes at room
131 temperature, after which another 0.1 ml of H₂O₂ addition was made [53,58–60]. This further
132 oxidation step with H₂O₂ was applied to ensure a complete dissolution of the recalcitrant or partially
133 digested polymer matrix.

134 After the different digestion protocols, the vessels were left cooling at room temperature, then
135 solutions were transferred to pre-cleaned low-density polyethylene (LDPE) bottles and diluted to 20
136 g with ultrapure water. These solutions were then filtered (0.22 μm PTFE filter), further 20-fold

137 diluted and spiked with two internal standards (Rh and Re, respectively). Lastly, solutions were
 138 analysed via ICP-MS using a He-collision cell in kinetic energy discrimination (KED) mode (Thermo
 139 Scientific ICAP Q). Settings and working parameters are depicted in Supplementary Materials (Table
 140 S3). External calibration was employed for element quantification. According to ERM[®]-EC681m, the
 141 analyses were validated over the seven previously listed metals (As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn;
 142 paragraph 2.1.) for which the content is certified.

143

144 **Table 1:** Summary of the protocols, conditions and acid mixtures applied in the current work for microwave-assisted
 145 acid digestions.

Protocol	Conditions	Acid mixture
1	Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C)	4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of 95% H ₂ SO ₄
1+H	1) Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C) 2) Room temperature	1) 4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of 95% H ₂ SO ₄ 2) 0.2 ml of 30% H ₂ O ₂
2	Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C)	4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of 37% HCl
2+H	1) Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C) 2) Room temperature	1) 4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of of 37% HCl 2) 0.2 ml of 30% H ₂ O ₂
3	Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C)	4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of 30% H ₂ O ₂
3+H	1) Microwave-assisted heating (200 °C) 2) Room temperature	1) 4 ml of 65% HNO ₃ and 1 ml of of 30% H ₂ O ₂ 2) 0.2 ml of 30% H ₂ O ₂

146

147 2.3. Analysis of solid residuals

148 In case of incomplete digestions showing visible solid residuals after the applied protocols, the solid
 149 residual was analysed for morphology and main chemical composition. The incompletely digested
 150 solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 minutes and the solution in excess was removed. Then,
 151 ca 200 µL of the solution with the residual was drop-casted on sample holders (covered with a

152 conductive carbon tape) for scanning electron microscope (SEM) and dried in an oven at 60 °C for
153 60 min. Samples were subsequently coated with a gold layer using a Cressington (UK) 108 auto
154 vacuum sputter coater to increase their conductivity. A field emission gun-SEM (Philips®,
155 Netherlands), with a 20 keV beam under high vacuum conditions, coupled with energy dispersive X-
156 ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDX) was then employed. This allowed to semi-quantitatively analyse the
157 elemental content of insoluble substances after sample incomplete digestions.

158

159 **2.4. Reagents, QA/QC procedures and data processing**

160 All operations regarding sample and solution preparations were carried out under a laminar flow
161 hood to avoid airborne contamination (aura HZ72T BIOAIR, Italy). Analytical grade reagents and
162 ultrapure water (Milli-Q from Sartorius Arium® mini, Germany; resistivity: 18.8 M U cm; TOC: <5
163 ppb) were used. Ultrapure HNO₃ and HCl were produced by sub-boiling distillation [61] from
164 commercial HNO₃ (Carlo Erba, 65% v/v) and HCl (Carlo Erba, 37% v/v) in a Milestone (USA) DuoPur
165 system, whereas H₂SO₄ (Analytika, 95% v/v pure) and H₂O₂ (Fisher Chemical, 30-32% v/v for trace
166 analysis) were purchased as they are. All LDPE containers (Nalgene®) employed for analytical
167 solutions underwent a cleaning procedure: firstly, they were rinsed with ultrapure water and
168 submerged in a 0.4% v/v detergent solution (Nalgene® L900) for one week; secondly, they were
169 rinsed with ultrapure water and soaked in a 2% v/v HNO₃ solution for another week and, after rinsing
170 with ultrapure water, they were left at drying under a laminar flow hood [62]. PTFE digestion vessels
171 were pre-cleaned before each digestion cycle following a two-step procedure: they were firstly
172 cleaned through a heating cycle with 65% HNO₃ and rinsed three-times with ultrapure water. Then,
173 they were conditioned through another heating cycle with the acid mixtures used for the following
174 protocol (depending on the one selected) and again rinsed three-times with ultrapure water. Multi-
175 element standard solutions were applied for external calibration of the ICP-MS measurements.

176 These were prepared by dilution of multi-elemental standard stock solutions (Merck KGaA
177 (Germany); Sigma-Aldrich (USA)).

178 The metals detected and quantified were As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn. Ti was also added to the
179 analytes list after SEM-EDX analysis of the elements in the residuals of end-use plastic sample
180 digestion.

181 The final metal concentrations were reported as milligrams of the extracted metal by kilogram of
182 the dry sample (mg kg^{-1}). Uncertainty of measures was calculated after the digestion of 6 replicates
183 and expressed as standard deviation [63]. Method detection limits (MDLs) were estimated by means
184 of method blanks: they were reported as the mean determined concentration plus three times the
185 standard deviation of a set of 6 method blanks and expressed as mg kg^{-1} based on a 100 mg solid
186 sample (Table S4). Potential contaminations during laboratory procedures were assessed by
187 analytical blanks.

188 Calculations were carried out using Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. Statistical analysis concerning
189 normality tests (Shapiro–Wilk test) and outlier evaluations (Grubbs test) was performed using Origin
190 2018 software (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, MA, USA). To quantitatively evaluate method
191 performance, measurement results were compared against the certified values in compliance with
192 the recommended guidelines [64]. ACD/ChemSketch molecular modelling software was used for
193 structure drawing of polymer materials.

194

195 **3. Results and discussion**

196 **3.1 Validation of digestion protocols with the CRM**

197 The six different protocols for microwave-assisted digestions were firstly applied for dissolution of
198 the CRM ERM[®]-EC681m. The performance of the protocols was validated for the certified values of
199 As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn and Zn and by observing the completeness of the sample dissolution.

200 Protocols 1, 2 and 3 (i.e., protocols not involving an additional digestion step with H₂O₂, Table 1)
201 provided recoveries that greatly ranged from 24.2 ± 3.0 % (Sn with protocol 3) to 101.0 ± 2.0 % (Sn
202 with protocol 1), depending upon the specific protocol and metal (Table S1). The overall average
203 recovery of all seven selected metals given by protocol 1 was 87.8 ± 5.6 %, while for protocol 2 it
204 was 91.8 ± 5.6 % and for protocol 3 it was 76.3 ± 25.8 % (Fig. 1a). For these three protocols, the only
205 few metals whose measured concentrations agreed with those certified were Pb with protocol 3
206 (96.3 ± 5.7 %, 67.1 ± 3.8 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1e) and Sn with protocol 1 (96.0 ± 4.0 %, 95 ± 4 mg kg⁻¹) and
207 protocol 2 (101.0 ± 2.0 %, 100 ± 2 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1g). This demonstrated that protocols 1, 2 and 3
208 were generally not successful for digestion of the CRM, except for these three specific cases.

209 The lowest recoveries were observed with protocol 3 on both Sn (24.2 ± 3.0 %, 24 ± 3 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig.
210 1g) and Sb (62.8 ± 3.5 %, 54 ± 3 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1f). Low values for Sb and Sn are linked to the absence
211 of halogens in the digestion solution which may, in fact, lead to losses of Sn and Sb due to the
212 formation of hydrolysis products [46,65]. Our results are consistent with studies in which a
213 combination of HNO₃ and HCl (similar to our protocol 2) was used to dissolve the same CRM used
214 in this study [37].

215 Considering, instead, the protocols which involved an additional digestion step with H₂O₂ (i.e., 1+H,
216 2+H and 3+H in Table 1), nearly all of them provided concentrations in agreement with the certified
217 values for all metals, with the only exceptions of protocol 3+H for As (87.9 ± 2.9 %, 14.9 ± 0.5 mg kg⁻¹)
218 (Fig. 1b), Sb (71.5 ± 4.7 %, 61 ± 4 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1f), Sn (30.0 ± 4.0 %, 30 ± 4 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1g) and Zn
219 (104.7 ± 3.8 %, 1225 ± 44 mg kg⁻¹) (Fig. 1h). The average recoveries for all seven selected metals
220 collectively were 100.0 ± 0.7 % for protocol 1+H, 100.2 ± 4.5 % for protocol 2+H and 85.7 ± 27.3 %
221 for protocol 3+H (Fig. 1a). As shown, most of the protocols with H₂O₂ final addition yielded higher
222 concentrations of metals after the digestions than protocols where H₂O₂ after digestion was not
223 employed. Declines in recoveries between the corresponding protocols with and without H₂O₂

224 ranged from ca -4 to -18 % depending on the specific metal and protocol. The results of the digestion
225 and analysis of metals in the CRM helped to evaluate the importance of H₂O₂ as an auxiliary reagent
226 in digestion procedures. Indeed, it is evident that H₂O₂ (used in protocols 1+H, 2+H and 3+H) played
227 an important role in the digestion of the CRM. The combination of H₂O₂ with other reagents during
228 digestions increased the oxidation of carbon to carbon dioxide and thus improved the digestibility
229 [57,66].

230 Sn was the sole exception, providing similar recovery rates with both protocols with and without
231 H₂O₂ and regardless of the acid mixture used (i.e., 1+H, 1, 2+H and 2 gave results that matched the
232 certified value) (Fig. 1g). For Pb, instead, both protocols 3+H and 3 offered values well in agreement
233 with those certified, although concentrations with 3+H were slightly higher (i.e., $71.8 \pm 2.7 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$
234 versus $67.1 \pm 3.8 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1e).

235 It is worth mentioning that the element specific trends observed for protocols 1, 2 and 3 are
236 remarked in the protocols 1+H, 2+H and 3+H. Comparing in fact the different reagents used in
237 combination with HNO₃ (i.e., protocols 1+H, 2+H and 3+H, Table 1), both protocols 1+H (HNO₃
238 combined with H₂SO₄ and H₂O₂) and 2+H (HNO₃ mixed with HCl and H₂O₂) yielded results in line with
239 the certified values of all considered metals (Fig. 1, Table S1). Specifically, protocol 1+H provided
240 recovery rates ranging from $98.6 \pm 3.1 \%$ for Cr ($44.5 \pm 1.4 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1d) to $101.0 \pm 2.3 \%$ for Sb
241 ($87 \pm 2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1f), whereas for protocol 2+H the lowest recovery was $93.1 \pm 6.3 \%$ for As (15.8
242 $\pm 1.0 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 1b) and the highest of $105.6 \pm 5.7 \%$ was observed for Sn ($105 \pm 6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig.
243 1g, Table S1). The standard deviations relative to Cd, Pb and Cr provided by protocol 2+H varied
244 from approximately 6.5 to 8.0 %. Protocol 3+H (HNO₃ mixed with H₂O₂) showed instead a generally
245 lower concentrations, especially for the metals analysed (i.e., As, Sn and Sb): only Cd, Cr and Pb
246 measurements agreed with the certified values with recoveries of $102.1 \pm 4.1 \%$ ($149 \pm 6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$),
247 $101.1 \pm 3.8 \%$ ($45.6 \pm 1.7 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), and $103.0 \pm 3.9 \%$ ($71.8 \pm 2.7 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), respectively (Fig.1, Table

248 S1). Recovery rate of Sb set at $70.9 \pm 4.7 \%$ ($61 \pm 4 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$), while the lowest of $30.3 \pm 4.0 \%$ (30 ± 4
249 mg kg^{-1}) was obtained for Sn. Concerning Sb, although not observed in this case, its recovery may
250 be also affected by the silica content of the matrix, as the formation of insoluble antimony-silicate
251 complexes in the presence of nitrogen acid is known to occur [69,70]. In our study, the higher
252 standard deviation of Sb with protocol 2+H could also be attributed to losses after the formation of
253 volatile species occurring when Sb (III) species are complexed by chloride ions [55].

254 Protocols 1+H and 2+H were instead validated for all the analysed metals. In more detail, 1+H
255 yielded improved accuracy and offered the lower standard deviations in all the digestion replicates,
256 hence leading to significant improvements in precision in comparison to the latter. This was
257 presumably due to a more efficient digestion of the matrix, as the application of 1+H consistently
258 provided visually clear solutions free of any noticeable precipitate. Our findings are in agreement
259 with previous research which revealed the advantages of H_2SO_4 (reagent used in protocol 1+H and
260 1) for polyethylene matrices, such as a decrease in the digestion time and a complete dissolution of
261 the sample [67]. H_2SO_4 is typically applied to enhance organic matter oxidation and increase the
262 boiling point of the acid mixture [52,54]. Hindrances in the proper quantification of some analytes
263 arising from this reagent (i.e., formation of insoluble sulphate salts or the potential generation of
264 non-spectral interferences in ICP-MS) [68] were not observed in the current work, at least for
265 protocols 1+H. The use of H_2SO_4 in our study led in fact to significantly improved overall results,
266 confirming suitability for all the seven considered metals. Besides, blank values and the
267 corresponding MDLs were not statistically different from the values obtained with other reagents
268 (Table S3). The discrepancies between Pb concentrations obtained with protocols 1+H and 1 (69.8
269 $\pm 0.9 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ against $60.4 \pm 2.6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, respectively) (Fig. 1e) may instead be justified by the
270 formation of lead sulphate salts with the protocol 1.

272 **Fig. 1:** Results of the seven selected metals (As, Cr, Cd, Pb, Sb, Sn, and Zn, displayed from panel a to h, respectively)
 273 obtained by the application of the six digestion protocols (namely, 1+H, 2+H, 3+H, 1, 2, and 3) on ERM®-EC681m. Panel
 274 a displays the average recoveries provided by each single protocol, calculated considering all seven metals collectively.
 275 For graphs b - h, the solid red line represents the certified value (unweighted mean) of the considered metal, with the
 276 corresponding uncertainty displayed with dashed red lines (expanded uncertainty of the certified value with a coverage

277 factor $k = 2$, corresponding to a level of confidence of 95 %). Measurement results are given with their average value (n
278 = 6) and uncertainty (confidence interval at 95%). Asterisk (*) indicate results for which evaluation proved no significant
279 difference between the measurement and the certified value (paragraph 2.4.).

280

281 **3.2. Analysis of commercially available end-use plastic materials**

282 Pursuing our aim of obtaining a digestion procedure working properly for plastic materials of
283 different nature, we then selected and analysed three materials commonly available on the market
284 (namely, one LDPE and two compostable plastic bags) (Fig. S1). For the LDPE material, FTIR analysis
285 confirmed its composition, as displayed by its recycling code, while the FTIR spectra of compostable
286 plastics showed that polybutylene adipate terephthalate (PBAT) and starch (TPS, thermoplastic
287 starch) are blended, as expected for this material (Fig. S2 and Fig. S3) [50,51,71]. Based on the more
288 reliable results obtained on the CRM with protocols 1+H and 2+H (which included a final H_2O_2
289 addition) (paragraph 3.1.), these two protocols were selected to be compared in the analysis of end-
290 use plastic materials (Fig. 2, Table S2). As a third method for comparison, we decided to maintain
291 the protocol 3+H: while in fact this protocol was validated for 3 metals only with the CRM, it
292 represents an extremely common protocol for the acid digestion of plastic samples [40,46].

293 Observing the concentration yielded by the analysis of LDPE, some differences arose after the
294 application of the three protocols. For example, Zn and Cd had higher concentrations with protocol
295 3+H (Zn: $190.8 \pm 5.8 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$; Cd: $0.110 \pm 0.006 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2, Table S2). For Sn, instead, while
296 concentrations with protocol 1+H ($0.66 \pm 0.04 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) and 2+H ($0.65 \pm 0.08 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) were similar,
297 3+H resulted in a lower concentration ($0.32 \pm 0.05 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2f): the trend of this element was
298 in line with what observed in the analysis of the CRM. The behaviour of Sb in the LDPE sample agreed
299 with the results of the CRM, too: protocol 1+H gave considerably higher values ($22.5 \pm 0.2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$)
300 as respect to 2+H ($11.3 \pm 7.3 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) and 3+H ($1.8 \pm 1.1 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2e).

301 Importantly, the standard deviations of most metals were minimized when protocol 1+H was
302 applied. This was probably due to a more effective digestion of the matrix in comparison with the
303 other protocols. The analysis of residuals performed with SEM clearly showed this phenomenon:
304 protocols 2+H and 3+H showed diffused depositions and fragments of undigested plastic material
305 (Fig. 3). Semi-quantitative analysis of metals in deposits through SEM-EDX revealed the presence Ca
306 and Ti as the main components of these deposits (Fig. S4). Ti was also quantified in the digestion
307 solutions of the three protocols via ICP-MS, showing in fact a great variance among digestion
308 protocols: protocol 1+H yielded a concentration of $3113.4 \pm 1152.5 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, while protocol 2+H gave
309 $164.3 \pm 78.6 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, and 3+H resulted in $42.3 \pm 12.2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2h, Table S2).

310 The two compostable plastic samples (No.1 and 2) showed even more pronounced differences in
311 the concentrations of the selected metals comparing the three protocols applied (Fig. 2, Table S2).
312 The metal contents were again generally higher when protocol 1+H was deployed in comparison to
313 other methods. Sn, for example, was highly affected by the methodology applied: for the
314 compostable bag No. 1 the content with 1+H resulted higher than that found with procedure 2+H
315 ($4.19 \pm 0.15 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ against $3.33 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) and more than three times the concentration
316 obtained from procedure 3+H ($1.34 \pm 0.23 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) (Fig. 2f). A similar trend was observed for the
317 compostable plastic bag No. 2. Sn results on end-use plastic materials confirmed what already
318 observed with digestion on the CRM: Protocol 3+H yielded a lower concentration in comparison to
319 the others. Besides, the measured concentration of Zn was slightly higher with 1+H for both
320 materials (Fig. 2g). Protocol 1+H offered similar results as 2+H concerning As ($0.17 \pm 0.06 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$
321 with 1+H versus $0.16 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ with 2+H for the compostable plastic bag No. 1, and $0.071 \pm$
322 0.034 mg kg^{-1} with 1+H versus $0.070 \pm 0.029 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ with 2+H for the compostable plastic bag No.
323 2, respectively), whereas 3+H yielded concentrations below the MDL for both bags (Fig. 2a).

324 The higher concentration yielded by protocol 1+H were again linked to a more efficient dissolution
325 of the sample matrix. This process was evident observing the presence of undigested residuals:
326 mixture 1+H gave always visually clear solutions without depositions after the digestion of the two
327 compostable plastic bags, whereas both mixture 2+H and 3+H left macroscopically evident residuals.
328 The occurring precipitates were investigated with SEM-EDX analysis (Fig. 3, Fig. S4). These showed
329 variable morphologies and chemical composition: they included particles with a major
330 carbonaceous composition, possibly representing undigested polymer matrix, along with other
331 inorganic particles that showed the presence of Ca, Ti and Pb. The latter probably originated from
332 powders added to the polymer matrix during formulation. As in the case of the end-use LDPE, also
333 Ti in the compostable plastic bags yielded different concentrations using the three digestion
334 protocols. For the compostable plastic bag No. 1, the concentration obtained by protocol 1+H was
335 $2408.3 \pm 213.5 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$, while 2+H resulted in $216.3 \pm 8.8 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ and 3+H in $182.9 \pm 7.2 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$.
336 Similarly, for compostable plastic bag No. 2 protocol 1+H yielded a Ti concentration of $1603.1 \pm$
337 259.0 mg kg^{-1} , 2+H gave $193.1 \pm 8.7 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ and 3+H resulted in $136 \pm 3.5 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$ (Fig. 2h, Table S2).
338 Other metals showed instead less evident trends. For example, results of Cd concentration fell
339 within the same ranges for all procedures and for both bags (Fig. 2b). Pb resulted in similar values
340 provided by all three mixtures, with procedure 1+H offering narrower standard deviations (Fig. 2d).
341 Cr, instead, showed higher variability in comparison to LDPE bags (Fig. 2c). This finding may be
342 attributed to losses of Cr originating from the formation of chromium carbide during the digestion
343 of the polymeric blend [72,73].

344

345

346 **Fig. 2:** Results of the analysed metals (from panel a to h) for end-use LDPE bag and compostable bags No. 1 and 2
 347 obtained via the digestion protocols 1+H, 2+H, and 3+H, respectively. Measurements are shown with their average value
 348 and uncertainty (confidence interval at 95%).

349

351

352 **Fig. 3:** SEM images of insoluble substances after incomplete digestions. Panels a and b display residuals of end-use LDPE
 353 bag, while c, d, e and f show the filtrates of the compostable plastic bag No. 1 and 2, respectively. Images refer solely to
 354 protocols for which evident residuals were observed.

355

356 3.3 Discrepancies between CRM and end-use plastic samples: the role of additives and their 357 chemical composition

358 The quantification of metals in plastic materials is a challenging task: the major hurdles are due to
 359 the intrinsic heterogeneity of the polymer matrix and the consequent uneven distribution of

360 additives [46,68]. These features hinder measurement accuracy and repeatability, requiring the
361 effects to be evaluated for each polymer under investigation [73–76].

362 The findings reported here revealed some marked differences when applying the same digestion
363 protocols to a CRM (in the specific case ERM[®]-EC681m) and to other end-use plastic samples, even
364 the one composed by the same polymer (LDPE and compostable plastics). A key finding is that while
365 most of the protocols gave comparable results to the CRM (e.g. protocols 1+H and 2+H), they yielded
366 instead concentration values that were less consistent with another of the protocols we tested (i.e.
367 protocol 1+H).

368 These differences rely on the different species present in the CRM in comparison with the
369 (unknown) chemical speciation of several additives contained in end-use plastic objects, as well as
370 by other compound likely present in end use plastic materials, making their matrix more
371 heterogenous. CRMs are in fact purposely produced to be analysed. Hence, the additives are known
372 and intended to be generally dissolvable by conventional digestion methods. For example, some
373 metal oxides used in the plastic industry (e.g., Cr₂O₃ and SnO₂) were substituted in the production
374 of the CRM used in this study with other metallic species (such as CaCrO₄ and SnS₂), given the easier
375 dissolvability in acids displayed by the latter [45]. In contrast, end-use plastics available on the
376 market typically contain more additives and processing aids of unknown nature, alongside
377 unreacted monomers and undesired contaminants. This further complicates the analysis of end-use
378 plastic materials in comparison to CRMs.

379 As a consequence, a general higher variance among replicates and different protocols was observed
380 for the end-use plastic objects in comparison with the CRM. While the CRM was in fact entirely
381 digested regardless of the protocol applied, the end-use materials were collectively more
382 recalcitrant and challenging to dissolve, yielding digests that greatly differed on the basis of the acid
383 mixture used.

384 Other constrains were related to sample homogeneity which resulted in higher variances among
385 samples in the end-use plastic materials. Homogeneity is a desired property of CRMs and is
386 experimentally assessed in order to determine the minimum sample intake to guarantee the
387 certified value within its stated uncertainty. Conversely, end-use plastic materials are more
388 heterogeneous by nature, with additives not evenly distributed in the matrix, a feature that hinders
389 measurements replicability [77].

390 The results of some of the analytes were instead particularly variable regardless of the plastic types.
391 Among these, Sb and Sn were two examples: their behaviour was similar for both the CRM and the
392 end-use materials analysed, with protocol 1+H and 2+H providing higher concentrations as respect
393 to 3+H. Recovery of these metals appeared thus not only affected exclusively by the matrix itself,
394 but also by the reagents used. This observation confirms an effect related to the chemical properties
395 of the analysed element, which of course need to be considered in order to select the proper
396 analytical protocol.

397 Another remarkable finding concerned the quantification of Ti in end-use plastics. Ti presence in
398 plastics is related to its use as a pigment and UV absorber, typically in the form of titanium dioxide
399 (TiO_2) [19]. In our work Ti residuals were observed in the digests of end-use LDPE and compostable
400 plastics. Ti was differently extracted and quantified with the three methods. TiO_2 is known to be not
401 completely solubilize by HNO_3 alone. Other auxiliary acids are therefore used to liberate the Ti
402 sequestered within the structure of very stable compounds. HF is an example, despite its hazardous
403 properties. As a substitute, H_2SO_4 was seen to facilitate the protonation of HNO_3 leading to the
404 formation of the nitronium ion, a highly reactive species able to react with the lattice structure of
405 TiO_2 [78,79]. Our results are in line with studies in which the use of H_2SO_4 digestion method
406 produced high recoveries of Ti.

407

408 **3.4. Current hindrances and future challenges in the analysis of metals in plastic**

409 At present no generally applicable harmonized method to determine metals in plastic materials
410 exists and, although different direct techniques have been deployed to analyse the total mass
411 fraction of metals in plastic polymers, acid digestions followed ICP-MS analyses still stand as the
412 most commonly used methods [37,40]. Since there is still no consensus about the acids and
413 conditions to use in order to dissolve plastic materials, the current work experimentally pointed out
414 how relevant the choice of a proper protocol for digestions is for the generation of comparable data.
415 From our findings, the mixture of H₂SO₄, HNO₃, and H₂O₂ (protocol 1+H) appeared as a technically
416 valuable method for quantifying As, Cd, Cr, Pb, Sb, Sn, Zn and Ti in LDPE and compostable plastics.
417 This protocol stands as a sound compromise to alternative techniques for the dissolution of most of
418 recalcitrant oxides which employ either unconventional dissolution techniques (i.e., extremely high
419 temperature) or other acids such as HF, whose corrosiveness requires an alternative instrumental
420 setup for the following ICP-MS analysis [80].

421 Another key issue to overcome, as observed by the discrepancies between CRMs and commercially
422 available plastic materials, is the lower accuracies and precisions yielded when applying validated
423 acid digestion protocols to end-use plastic samples. Besides the different polymer matrices which
424 may require specific digestion protocols to ensure a proper dissolution of the metals, a key role of
425 the chemical features of the inorganic additives have been highlighted in this study. As such, while
426 additives readily dissolvable as in the CRM were accurately quantified by several different protocols,
427 more marked differences were observed in their application to end-use plastic samples. This may
428 apply also for other polymers: we therefore support future studies investigating the reliability of
429 acid digestions for dissolving also obstinate and chemically resistant matrices, in order to accurately
430 extract all relevant metals.

431 These issues clearly also apply to plastics collected from the environment. Environmental plastics
432 may be even more complex than pristine end-use plastic materials: they may not only contain the
433 metals added during manufacturing, but also those acquired from the environmental media where
434 they ended up. Concentration of these enriched metals can be much lower than the one analysed
435 in this study, requiring robust and well-established methods [24,81]. Environmental plastic samples,
436 in addition, may undergo aging, which results in a partial degradation of the polymeric matrix and
437 enhanced leaching of some of the additives present in the polymer matrix, as well as in the potential
438 change of their chemical speciation [82]. All these features will further complicate the application
439 of analytical protocols.

440

441 **4. Conclusions**

442 This study reports a comprehensive comparison of different digestion protocols to analyse metals
443 in different plastic samples, as a matrix of ever-increasing interest. We offered insights toward a
444 potential harmonization of methods through the comparison of different analytical protocols, as no
445 fully validated procedures for this analysis exist at present. Among the protocols tested for digesting
446 our end-use plastic materials, we recommend the use of H₂SO₄, HNO₃ and H₂O₂ mixture (protocol
447 1+H) for achieving a complete dissolution. However, uncertainties still lie in the complex and
448 heterogenous suite of inorganic additives which are commonly present in environmental plastics. It
449 is thus suggested to produce reference materials with loaded additives remarking the possible
450 composition of end-use plastic materials, as well as chemically aged polymers. These may be more
451 environmentally relevant to evaluate the effects of plastic pollution.

452 In conclusion we suggest further comparison studies on different plastics to move towards
453 harmonized and comparable data, ultimately contributing to a better understanding of the
454 interactions between metals in plastic materials and the likely environmental implications.

455

456 **Supplementary materials and data**

457 Electronic supporting information contains Tables S1-S4 and Figs. S1-S4.

458

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